

Spatial Analysis-Driven Facility Location Optimization for Vertiports

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Abstract—Innovative Air Mobility (IAM) integrates vertical take-off and landing (VTOL)-capable aircraft (VCA), specifically electric VTOLs (eVTOLs), into urban and suburban transportation systems and infrastructure. The success of this integration depends on the strategic placement of takeoff/landing sites (vertiports), representing central nodes for IAM operations. This study presents a two-step optimization approach for allocating demand from urban subareas to potential vertiport locations. In the first step, spatial analysis and Anselin Local Moran’s I clustering method are used to identify candidate vertiport points. In the second step, a linear location allocation model is developed to assign these demand points to the most suitable vertiports while considering operational constraints such as VTOL flight range. A case study in Saxony, Germany, demonstrates how demand distribution and accessibility influence vertiport selection. By integrating technological and urban planning constraints, this study provides a structured approach to optimizing IAM networks, supporting systematic and scalable IAM infrastructure planning.

Keywords—Vertiport Location Optimization; Facility Location Problem (FLP); Geospatial Analysis; Spatial Statistics; Moran’s I Spatial Autocorrelation

I. INTRODUCTION

Innovative Air Mobility (IAM) represents a vision for the future of urban transportation, incorporating electrical vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) aircraft — a specific category within the broader class of VTOL - capable aircraft (VCA)— into multimodal transport systems.

The successful deployment of IAM depends on a robust and efficient infrastructure, with vertiports serving as nodes for operations, passenger transfer, and vehicle maintenance. The strategic placement of vertiports must balance user accessibility, compliance with regulatory and safety requirements, integration with existing transportation systems, and urban planning constraints. Demand patterns vary over time and geography, adding complexity due to the dynamic and multimodal nature of urban mobility.

Research has explored various aspects of IAM implementation; however, limited attention has been given to the allocation of mixed urban and rural demand to potential vertiport locations and the assessment of their significance within the network (e.g., [1, 2]). This study optimizes the allocation of IAM traffic demand to potential vertiport locations through a

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Figure 1. Map of Saxony showing selected vertiport facilities (blue circles), which were chosen from the candidate vertiport facilities; unselected facilities (pinkish orange squares); assigned points (purple dots), which represent the demand points assigned to the selected vertiport facilities, and their connections (blue lines), indicating the link between the assignment points and the selected vertiport facilities.

two-step approach: clustering locations and assigning them to vertiport candidates using a linear optimization model. The framework identifies the optimal vertiport configuration by prioritizing sites that best meet demand while minimizing travel distances and adhering to constraints. Its key contributions include the development of this optimization framework and an analysis of urban demand patterns influencing vertiport selection and hierarchy. This work is part of a PhD research focused on optimizing IAM networks under multidisciplinary considerations, including technological, regulatory, and urban planning dimensions. The focus of our case study will be a potential IAM network in Saxony, Germany, as shown in Figure 1.

II. STATE-OF-THE-ART

Current research integrates Geographic Information System (GIS)-based spatial analysis, optimization models, and mixed-method approaches for spatial location planning. However, a framework that synthesizes spatial, regulatory, and operational constraints remains an ongoing challenge for vertiport planning.

GIS has become important in vertiport location planning, using spatial data to assess site suitability. Studies by [3] and [2] demonstrated how GIS tools identify high-priority vertiport locations based on proximity to demand centers and integration with public transit systems. Wu and Zhang [4] identified potential vertiport locations using a 3D GIS map created from lidar data, taking into account the physical and regulatory constraints in the selection of these locations. GIS-based frameworks often incorporate multicriteria decision-making, considering land use, accessibility, and environmental factors [5, 6]. Postal code data are widely used in GIS-based analyses to understand demographic patterns and demand behavior [7], finally improving demand estimation and site selection. Despite their effectiveness, GIS tools have limitations in handling multi-objective optimization and lack flexibility for dynamic urban conditions [8].

Optimization models, such as Facility Location Problem (FLP), have also gained prominence for the implementation of IAM. Zhao and Feng [1] proposed a strategic model for vertiport placement within multimodal transportation systems, focusing on travel time reduction and congestion mitigation. Further, while Wu and Zhang (2021) present a detailed optimization model based on simulated demand within a single-city context, our study addresses both urban and rural areas using spatial clustering and socio-demographic indicators. Additionally, Volakakis and Mahmassani [9]’s study highlighted the importance of a data-driven approach integrated with the transportation network by comparing various optimization models. Braßel et al. [10] solved an optimization problem for the location of a UAV hangar for rescue missions by using a shortest path approach. To enhance the effectiveness of these models, mixed methods improve model sensitivity by considering user behavior and demand elasticity [11]. This approach allows for a more comprehensive analysis of the complex factors involved in IAM planning.

Beyond optimization models, the literature also explores GIS-based spatial analysis and mixed-method frameworks. GIS methods support the evaluation of spatial features; optimization models rely on measurable indicators; and mixed-method approaches incorporate variability into decision-making processes. Although each method provides data-driven insights within its specific domain, current approaches remain limited in addressing the interdependencies among spatial, operational, and regulatory parameters in a unified manner. This indicates the continuing need for integrated and interdisciplinary frameworks capable of capturing the multilayered structure of innovative air mobility systems.

III. GIS BASED VERTIPORT ALLOCATION

This study addresses the problem of vertiport allocation by utilizing a FLP framework to optimize the placement of vertiports, minimizing total travel distance (from demand points to selected vertiports and, between interconnected vertiports) while satisfying demand and operational constraints. We adhere to the FLP terminology, where a demand point represents a location that generates flight demand, and a candidate facility denotes a potential vertiport site.

Figure 2. A model integrating data processing, input data preparation, and modeling to minimize costs for optimal facility placement, customer assignments, and facility connections.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the first step involves integrating and enriching geospatial data to define demand points based on workplace density and candidate facility locations based on population density. This approach is grounded in the assumption that, in the absence of individual-level travel flow data, spatial concentrations of population and employment can serve as proxies for potential user behavior. In this context, workplaces are treated as attraction centers, reflecting the premise that areas with high employment density are likely to generate greater mobility demand.

Next, candidate facility locations are identified using Anselin Local Moran’s I Cluster and Outlier Analysis, which detects spatial clusters of high or low population density areas. This step reduces the solution space, potentially improving computational efficiency in data-intensive scenarios and enabling demand aggregation around strategically located vertiports.

Finally, the optimal selection of facility locations, demand point assignments, and facility interconnections are determined while considering the range and costs associated with both customer-to-facility and facility-to-facility interactions.

A. Data Integration and Spatial Analysis Processes

The initial phase entails obtaining Postcode5 datasets in Shapefile format. These datasets are enhanced with attributes, such as population and workplace counts, using Esri ArcGIS

Pro 3.3 and Nexiga GmbH datasets. Postcode fields are transformed into point datasets using geographical centroids.

Workplace numbers per postcode area are used as demand values for the FLP analysis. Demand Points represent these demand values as a set of customers I . Some of these demand points can also be facilities, forming set J .

1) Identification of Candidate Facilities:

a) *Spatial Autocorrelation*: Spatial autocorrelation aids in identifying population distribution patterns, guiding decisions on the placement of new facilities or services. Moran's I is a preferred statistic for spatial autocorrelation analysis due to its precision, interpretability, and consistency with other indices Gedamu et al. [12]. The study utilized both *Global* and *Local Moran's I* analyses to assess spatial autocorrelation in population distribution. The insights from these analyses help optimize location choices to enhance accessibility and efficiency.

b) *Global Moran's I*: Global Moran's I was computed using ArcGIS Pro 3.3, applying Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) and the Euclidean distance metric (cf., ??) to evaluate clustering tendencies. This analysis determined whether population distribution follows a random pattern or distinct spatial clusters.

c) *Anselin Local Moran's I*: Anselin's Local Moran's I further analyzed spatial clustering using IDW and Euclidean distance to classify population variations, pinpointing specific clusters of high or low population densities. The analysis produced the Local Moran's I value, z-score, p-value, and cluster type for each point. The results supported the identification of candidate facilities (J) as potential vertiport locations.

B. Distance Matrices

The spatial relationships between demand points ($i \in I$) and candidate facilities ($j \in J$), as well as between candidate facilities, were analyzed using distance matrices calculated based on the Euclidean distance on the UTM plane. These matrices were used to evaluate demand point accessibility and assess the candidate facilities for the range of eVTOL flights (R) between locations.

C. Location Allocation Model

The Location Allocation Model optimizes the assignment of demand points to candidate facilities and the connections between candidate facilities using a FLP formulation. The model comprises two sub-models:

1) Demand Points to Candidate Facilities Assignment:

This sub-model, using the Weighted Median Method, optimizes candidate facility assignments by minimizing the total weighted travel distance (c_{ij}). It considers demand points (i), the count of workplace (w_i , used as a weight), and the travel distances (d_{ij}). This approach ensures that each demand point (i) is assigned to exactly one candidate facility (j), and assignments are limited to selected facilities.

The weighted distance c_{ij} for demand point-candidate facility pair ij is:

$$c_{ij} = w_i \cdot d_{ij} \quad (1)$$

2) *Candidate Facility to Candidate Facilities Link Optimization*: This sub-model enhances operational efficiency by optimizing connections between candidate facilities while respecting eVTOL flying range constraints. Travel distances between facilities are minimized, ensuring feasible connections within vehicle flying range limits.

3) *Solving the Model*: The optimization model was implemented using the Pyomo library and solved using the CPLEX optimization solver. The objective function minimizes the distances between assignment points and facilities, as well as the connection costs between facilities. The result determines the selection of facilities from the candidate facilities, assignment of demand points, and connections between facilities. Specifically, when $y_j = 1$ for a facility j , it indicates that this location has been chosen as a selected facility from the candidate facilities. Facilities not chosen remain as unselected facilities. The model also establishes connections between the assignment points and the selected facilities.

D. Location Model Formulation

The general FLP [13] determines optimal locations for facilities location to serve a set of customers while minimizing overall costs. Our model is based on the FLP and minimizes the total weighted distance between customers and facilities while considering constraints such as eVTOL flying range, facility opening costs, and connectivity between facilities. Below are the key elements of the FLP used and their definitions:

• Sets:

- I : Set of customers ($i \in I$).
- J : Set of candidate facilities ($j \in J$).

• Decision Variables:

- $x_{ij} \in 0, 1$: Binary variable indicating whether demand point i is assigned to candidate facility j .
- $y_j \in 0, 1$: Binary variable indicating whether candidate facility j is chosen/selected.
- $z_{ij} \in 0, 1$: Binary variable indicating if a connection exists between two facilities.

• Parameters:

- d_{ij} : The distance between location i and location j .
- c_{ij} : Weighted distance for assigning demand point i to candidate facility j , calculated using demand weights.
- R : Maximum flying range of the eVTOL.

The objective function in Equation (2) minimizes the total weighted distance and the facility-to-facility connection costs:

$$\min \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in J} c_{ij} x_{ij} + \sum_{i \in J} \sum_{j \in J, i \neq j} d_{ij} z_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Sub to:

$$\sum_{j \in J} x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i \in I \quad (3)$$

$$x_{ij} \leq y_j, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall j \in J \quad (4)$$

$$z_{ij} d_{ij} \leq R, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall j \in J \quad (5)$$

$$z_{ij} \leq y_i, \quad z_{ij} \leq y_j, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall j \in J \quad (6)$$

The assignment constraint Equation (3) ensures that each demand point i must be assigned to exactly one chosen facility j . Equation (4) guarantees that demand points can only be assigned to facilities that are chosen/selected. Equation (5) enforces that facility-to-facility connections are only valid if the distance between them does not exceed the maximum flying range of the eVTOL. Finally, Equation (6) ensures that facility-to-facility connections can only occur between facilities that are chosen/selected. Typical linear programming techniques can be used to solve the problem.

IV. RESULTS

The study was carried out in Saxony, Germany, covering an area of 18,420 km². Saxony has a population of 4.055 million and is divided into seven regions, with Dresden as the state capital, and Leipzig and Chemnitz as other major urban centers. In order to ensure accurate spatial analysis within this diverse landscape, the study used the 'EPSG:32633 - WGS 84 / UTM zone 33N' coordinate system.

According to the cluster and assignment approach, fig. 1 illustrates that larger cities exhibit a concentration of selected facilities with several assigned demand points connected to each chosen vertiport. High-density demand clusters, such as those ones around Dresden and Leipzig, tend to be assigned multiple vertiports to ensure adequate coverage and minimize passenger travel distances.

Conversely, regions with lower demand densities exhibit fewer selected facilities, focusing on optimizing coverage with fewer locations. This distribution aligns with the spatial autocorrelation analysis, where High-High clusters (HH) correspond to the areas with the highest vertiport selection rates.

In conclusion, multiple vertiports in high-demand urban areas are essential to meet the operational needs of IAM, while rural regions can be served effectively with fewer facilities, optimizing accessibility and network efficiency.

A. Global Moran's I

Global Moran's I analysis revealed a statistically significant clustering in the spatial distribution of the population (Moran's I = 0.243369, z-score = 9.814127, $p < 0.01$). A positive Moran's I value indicates that similar customer densities tend to cluster in spatially close locations. The high z-score and very low p-value indicate that the probability of the clustering pattern arising by random chance is less than 1%.

B. Anselin Local Moran's I

The Anselin Local Moran's I Analysis revealed distinct spatial patterns in population distribution. The results identified 52 High-High (HH) and 44 Low-Low (LL) clusters, along with 12 High-Low (HL) and 8 Low-High (LH) outliers. Additionally, 163 points showed no spatial dependence. These findings indicate clear hotspots and cold spots in the population distribution. This distribution aligns with the spatial autocorrelation analysis, where High-High clusters (HH) correspond to the areas with the highest vertiport selection rates. For the purpose of identifying potential vertiport locations,

only HH, HL, and LH values were considered relevant. LL clusters, non-significant points, and areas without neighbors were excluded from further analysis. Outliers (HL and LH) were retained for potential future in-depth studies, allowing for a focused yet flexible approach to vertiport site selection.

C. Location Allocation

The location-allocation model efficiently assigned 385 demand points to 51 selected vertiports from a pool of 72 candidates, minimizing overall costs. As shown in Figure 1, the selected facilities are primarily concentrated in major cities, reflecting their role as central hubs. The surrounding areas emerge as catchment zones, with demand points assigned accordingly. This spatial structure highlights the model's role in capturing urban-rural interactions.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study developed a methodological framework for optimizing the allocation of demand points to candidate facilities by applying spatial clustering and facility location modeling to improve location decisions. The approach emphasizes the importance of identifying potential demand points in regions with uncertain demand, highlighting the need for high-quality spatial datasets and accurate metrics to enhance spatial clustering and decision-making. This study adopts a point-based, static demand modeling approach, where demand is represented by discrete nodes corresponding to spatial attractors. These demand points, although not incorporating temporal variation or individual-level behavior, provide a macroscopic perspective suitable for evaluating potential vertiport locations within the area. Furthermore, it underscores the necessity of a structured, computationally efficient approach to location optimization.

Our methodology builds upon existing GIS-based analyses and optimization models discussed in the literature, addressing some of their limitations. While GIS tools have proven effective for spatial analysis our approach integrates optimization techniques to handle multi-objective spatial planning scenarios with greater flexibility and precision. Similarly, our model extends traditional facility location problems by incorporating spatial clustering, thus providing a more comprehensive framework for vertiport planning.

While the study focused on Saxony, the region's boundaries were not imposed as constraints, and aviation restrictions or accessibility criteria were not considered when assigning demand points to facilities. Also, factors such as flight safety, noise pollution, urban development, and electricity infrastructure are excluded from the model. Due to the absence of specific demand point data, socio-demographic information was used as a proxy. However, a key limitation is the lack of traffic flow data, which, if incorporated, could provide a more detailed and realistic representation of demand distribution.

The current model simplifies eVTOL vehicles by using a static maximum range. In reality, the range of eVTOLs varies based on payload, weather conditions, operational profile, and even on battery degradation, which are not captured in the current model.

The proposed model is flexible and adaptable, with the potential to evolve through the integration of additional data sources. This flexibility aims to address the identified need for integrated planning frameworks that account for the interdependencies among spatial, operational, and regulatory parameters.

Future research should focus on incorporating traffic flow data to enhance demand estimation, conducting realistic accessibility analyses to refine location assignments, and considering operational constraints, such as vertiport capacity. These advancements would contribute to more robust and data-driven location strategies to foster efficient facility placement decisions.

This study contributes to research on vertiport location planning by presenting an integrated approach that combines spatial analysis with optimization techniques. Although the current model is based on specific assumptions, it provides a scalable and adaptable foundation for further studies and potential real-world applications within the field of innovative air mobility.

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